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Closing programme and travelling exhibition

Deliverables 3.7, 3.7.1, 3.7.2, 3.7.3

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A-Place

Deliverables 3.7, 3.7.1, 3.7.2, 3.7.3

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Editors:

Leandro Madrazo

Contributors:

Maria Irene Aparicio

Leandro Madrazo

Petra Pferdmenges

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Executive Summary

This report includes the combined activities “Traveling Exhibition” (Deliverable 3.7) and “Closing programme” (Deliverables 3.7.1, 3.7.2 and 3.7.3).

To share the outcomes of the project and reflect on the collaborative work with diverse stakeholders involved in artistic and educational activities within communities, we organized “A Wrap up” programme consisting of three closing events in Brussels, Barcelona, and Lisbon. In conjunction with these events, we displayed an exhibition featuring the collective work in the cities and other partner locations.

The three closing events were the following:

- **Co-constructing lived spaces, Brussels, 26 May 2023.** The role of placemaking in promoting participatory design, spatial justice, and the appropriation of public space.
- **A place in Can Trinxet, L’Hospitalet (Barcelona), June 3 2023.** The importance of educational and creative activities in public spaces to engage artists and creators from all academic levels, in the creation of places.
- **Sensing places together, Lisbon, 14-15 September 2023.** Representing a sense of place through various art forms, such as music, photography, video, and artistic performance.

The chosen venues for the three events hold significant historical value, having been repurposed from old structures rich with memories to new cultural and social centres. [La Serre](#), once a warehouse in Brussels, was transformed into an artist workshop and socio-cultural gatherings. [Can Trinxet](#), a former textile factory in L’Hospitalet (Barcelona), now serves as a community centre claimed by locals as a social and cultural hub. And, [Largo do Cabeço da Bola](#) in Lisbon, a former garrison, has been managed by a cultural and socially responsible cooperative.

The final exhibition consists of 13 panels which summarize the work done by the consortium over the last four years, and highlight the connections across the activities carried out in multiple places, and with various formats. The panels are available in the Annex of this document.

Introduction

The purpose of the closing events in Brussels, Barcelona, and Lisbon was to showcase and disseminate the work carried out during the project and to share and discuss it with other agents involved in community development through artistic and educational practices. In conjunction with these events, an exhibition of the collective work was on display.

The gatherings brought together project partners, invited experts, and community representatives to discuss key issues related to the project and the achieved results. The three closing events focused on a specific theme:

- **Co-constructing lived spaces, Brussels.** The role of placemaking in promoting participatory design, spatial justice, and the appropriation of public space.
- **A place in Can Trinxet, L'Hospitalet (Barcelona).** The importance of educational and creative activities in public spaces to engage artists and creators from all academic levels, in the creation of places.
- **Sensing places together, Lisbon.** Representing a sense of place through various art forms, such as music, photography, video, and artistic performance.

This document summarizes the activities that took place in each closing event. A video reportage of each event is also available in the A-Place website.

1.1 Purpose and target group

The purpose of the three closing events was to disseminate the A-Place results that had been produced over the last four years. In order to do so, each of the responsible host partners in Brussels, Barcelona and Lisbon defined a concept and location for the event and exhibition. All three closing events were organized in locations with a particular significance for the local communities: the community centre "La Serre", in Brussels; the old textile factory "Can Trinxet" in L'Hospitalet, and "Largo Residencias", and artistic creation and community involvement centre located in an old garrison. Guest speakers and local artists were invited to participate in these events, along with A-Place partners.

1.2 Contribution of partners

Alive Architecture, La Salle-URL and NOVA were in charge of organizing their respective events in Brussels, Barcelona and Lisbon. La Salle-URL designed and produced the panels of the final exhibitions. Partners attended the closing events in Brussels (Alive Architecture, KU Leuven, Prostoroz, University of Ljubljana, La Salle-URL), Barcelona (La Salle-URL, Screen Projects, NOVA) and Lisbon (NOVA, La Salle-URL, Prostoroz, University of Ljubljana).

1. Closing Event Brussels: Co-constructing lived spaces

Petra Pferdmenges & Juliette Marchand
Alive Architecture

1.1 Introduction

The A-Place closing event in Brussels took place on May 26, 2023, from 9:30 am to 7:00 pm at La Serre, a community centre coordinated by the NGO Communa. Approximately 30 participants attended the event, with the number varying throughout the day and reaching up to 150 people during the closing concert. A flyer, containing a project description, the day's program, and basic information on where to find more information about the project, was distributed to all participants (Figures 1.1-1.2).

The A-Place partners participating in this closing event were Petra Pferdmenges and Juliette Marchand from Alive Architecture, as hosts, together with Leandro Madrazo from the School of Architecture La Salle; Masa Cvetko and Vesna Skubic from Prostorož; Rosie Romero, from KU Leuven Department of Architecture, and Nina Povse from the Faculty of Architecture, University of Ljubljana. Partners presented a summary of the work done in the project during the morning session.

In addition to the A-Place members, the programme included presentations by local groups committed to the task of reappropriating public space. The following presentations were delivered in the afternoon session:

- Bram Dewolfs from [Urban Foxes](#), a multi-disciplinary placemaking collective based in Brussels
- Lisa Pleysier from [Park Poétik](#) which organizes workshops, interactive shows, concerts, visual installations and parades in collaboration with artists, residents and local cultural organizations
- Antoine Dutrieu, from the non-profit organization [Communa](#), committed to social transitional urbanism

A video documentary of the event is available [here](#).

Figures 1.1-1.2. Flyer handed-out to all participants

1.2 Programme development

The day commenced with an informal presentation, as all participants gathered in a circle facilitated by Charlotte Bens of Communa, serving as the team dynamizer.

The block of morning presentations started with an introduction of the project by Leandro Madrazo, from the School of Architecture La Salle-URL, project coordinator (Figure 1.3).

Figure 1.3. Leandro Madrazo introduces the A-Place project to all participants

A-Place partners presented then their work and discussed it with the participants.

Nina Povse from the Faculty of Architecture (Figure 1.4), University of Ljubljana presented the project [“A Re-Place”](#) developed together with Prostorož and a group of university students. During a five-day workshop the group co-designed and co-constructed a series of urban installations on the Krater site in Ljubljana.

Figure 1.4. Presentation by Nina Povse

The second presentation was given by Maša Cvetko from Prostorož (Figure 1.5). Maša provided a brief overview of the history of playgrounds before presenting the playscape they designed and constructed (Figures 1.6, 1.7). Then she introduced the “A-Pla(y)ce” programme (Figures 1.8-1.13), which was implemented at the Krater site in Ljubljana in 2021, involving students from the Faculty of Architecture. As a result of the activities, new playground structures were built in the area (Figures 14, 15).

Figure 1.5. Presentation by Maša Cvetko

Figures 1.6, 1.7. A short history of playground design

Figures 1.8-1.13. "A Re-Place" workshop on the Krater site in Ljubljana

Figure 1.14-1.15. Play installations on the Krater site, Ljubljana

Leandro Madrazo, from the School of Architecture La Salle, presented the work carried out in [“A Weaved Place”](#) in the city of L’Hospitalet de Llobregat, located in the Barcelona metropolitan area. The collaborative effort involved architecture students, high school pupils from local schools, their tutors, and guest artists. The architecture students conducted a visual analysis of the neighbourhoods, creating a map of the city as a collage with the photographic survey (Figures 1.16, 1.17). Local students identified relevant public spaces which embodied personal memories. Subsequently, they collaboratively designed and executed on-site interventions to re-signify these public spaces (Figures 1.18-1.21). At the end of the programme, the public art festival ES_CULTURA, organized with the collaboration of the municipality, transformed a square of the Bellvitge neighbourhood into a canvas for artistic exploration (Figures 1.22, 1.23).

Figure 1.16-1.17. Collaborative mapping with collage techniques, by students of the School of Architecture La Salle

Figure 1.18-1.21. Interventions in public space, collaboratively designed and built by architecture students and local high school pupils

Figure 1.22.. "Fill the void", a work by Anna Trasserra, School of Architecture La Salle, at the ES_CULTURA festival

Figure 1.23. "Bureau", a work of Nerea Mejías, Inês Moxo, María Rosa Gavin and Paula Díaz, School of Architecture La Salle, at the ES_CULTURA festival

The fourth presentation by A-Place partners was given by Rosaura Romero, representing the Department of Architecture at KU Leuven. Rosaura introduced the project "[A Place of Our Own,](#)" implemented at the homeless shelter Foyer Bodegem in Brussels. The project aimed to promote architectural design justice by aiding residents in enhancing the indoor spaces of the shelter through collaboration with architecture students (DIWPO - do it with others) (Figure 1.24). The collectively painted walls and crafted furniture made from repurposed materials found within the building. This activity fostered an increased sense of belonging and collective identity among the residents (Figure 1.25).

Figure 1.24. DIWO workshop at the Foyer Bodegem

Figure 1.25. Painting on the wall with photo of the team

The final presentation by A-Place partners was given by the representative of Alive Architecture. The presentation centred around [“A Happy Place”](#) in Brussels, where, in collaboration with Bravvo, co-produced a series of small interventions in the public spaces of the Dardaar district (Figures 1.26-1.31). The objective was to foster a sense of ownership with the public space among the residents and their children residing in the surrounding housing blocks.

Figure 1.26-1.31. Urban interventions in the public spaces of the Dardaar district

The presentations by A-Place partners were followed by a lunch prepared for all participants by Bouche Oreille, an NGO based in Brussels (Figure 1.32).

Figure 1.32. Lunch at La Serre

After the lunch break, the three invited speakers presented their work with communities in public spaces. Each presentation was followed by a discussion.

The first speaker was Bram Dewolfs from [Urban Foxes](#), a multi-disciplinary placemaking collective based in Brussels, with team members from around the world (Figures 1.33-1.38). The team creates and facilitates innovative and inclusive projects, workshops, and lectures in various countries. Bram presented a series of projects realized over the last years. One project with significant impact was "Picnics the streets" in front of the Bourse, which later inspired the transformation of Brussels centre into a pedestrian area.

Figure 1.33-1.38. From "Picnic the streets" (2012) to a city centre without cars in Brussels (2021)

The second speaker was Lisa Pleyzier from [Park Poëtik](#) (Figure 1.39) a collective that organizes workshops, interactive shows, concerts, visual installations, and parades in collaboration with artists, residents, and local cultural organizations. Essentially, their goal is to bring together people in public spaces through urban activities. During the lecture, Lisa introduced us to Park Poëtik and presented a series of artistic interventions realized over the last years.

Figure 1.39. Presentation by Lisa Pleysier from Park Poëtik

Figure 1.40-1.43. Some extracts of the presentation of Park Poëtik, by Lisa Pleysier

Figure 1.44-1.45. Some extracts of the presentation of Park Poëtik, by Lisa Pleysier

The final speaker was Antoine Dutrieu from the non-profit organization [Communa](#), which facilitates social transitional urbanism. Communa's primary tool is temporary occupation. Antoine began by highlighting the abundance of vacant spaces and the existing housing needs in Brussels before providing examples of social temporary occupation. He also emphasized the benefits from such temporary use for users, owners, public authorities, and neighbourhoods (Figures 1.46-1.49).

Figure 1.46. The activities of Communa in Brussels

Figure 1.47. La Serre, an example of revitalization of a derelict structure in the heart of Brussels

Figure 1.48-1.49. Projects by Communa

After the presentations and discussions, participants moved to a nearby outdoor space, where they were divided into teams to discuss two questions (Figures 1.50, 1.51):

1. How can we invite citizens to appropriate public space?

Figure 1.50. Output of the round table “How can we invite citizens to appropriate public space?”

2. How can we assure the inclusiveness of artistic urban interventions ?

Figure 1.51. Output of the round table “How can we generate inclusiveness of artistic urban interventions?”

Each group changed the topic of discussion after twenty minutes (Figure 1.52). The animators of the tables, Juliette Marchand and Petra Pferdmeiges, synthesized the findings. The session concluded with an exchange of impressions about the presentations delivered during the day.

Figure 1.52. Round table with participants to reflect upon the output of the closing conference.

1.3 Concert

Back to La Serre, the day was finished during a drink and a concert of the Brussels based world-music trio [Peixe e Limão](#) (Figure 1.56).

Figure 1.56. A music soiree with Peixe e Limao

1.4 Exhibition

The closing exhibition in Brussels took place at the Department of Architecture at KU Leuven and ran from May 22 to June 9, 2023. The exhibition comprised 13 A0 panels that summarized the project activities undertaken by partners over the past four years, and their connections (Figures 1.53, 1.54). Additionally, it featured the projection of five "[Thematic videos](#)," produced at the end of the first two years of the project (Figure 1.55).

The panels and video projections were strategically placed in the multi-use space on the ground floor of the building, serving as a lobby, working area, exhibition room, and cafeteria. This location was chosen to ensure the maximum exposure of the exhibition.

Figure 1.53, 1.54. Panels at the exhibition at KU Leuven, Department of Architecture.

Figure 1.55. Closing exhibition at KU Leuven, Department of Architecture. Video projections

2. Closing Event Barcelona: A Place in Can Trinxet

Leandro Madrazo, Ángel Martín, Mario Hernández
School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona

2.1 Introduction

The closing event took place from June 3 at Can Trinxet, a restored old textile factory building now serving as a community space (Figure 2.1). The municipality of L'Hospitalet, and the Centre Cultural Santa Eulàlia, which oversees the management of the equipment, made the venue available for the event. An exhibition of the A-Place project, which remained open from June 3 to 7, was part of the programme (Figure 2.2).

Figure 2.1 Entry to the Can Trinxet premises, with the programme of the closing event

The one-day programme included debates, music performances, participatory creative activities, students' presentations, a sensorial workshop and, to finalize, a concert.

The debates were organized into three panels:

- Creating learning spaces
- The sense of place and audiovisual language
- Art, activism and public space

A series of music and dance performances took place during the event.

Attendees of the debates and exhibition had the opportunity to participate in a sensory exploration workshop of the space and in creating a collage using images from the city.

between academia and society, encouraging collaboration between different educational levels as well as between experts and non-experts.

Figure 2.3. Debate on "Creating learning places"

- "Art, activism, and public space"

Participants: Laura Garcimartín (Colectivo La Circolaxa), Ivone Ferreira (Universidade Nova), Erica Hassan (Fundación Contorno Urbano), Nevenka Pavic (La Gloria Factoría de Arte). Moderated by Miquel García.

In this dialogue, the complex relationship between art, activism, and community engagement were explored (Figure 2.4). Participants highlighted the active role of the community in shaping public spaces, emphasizing the need for meaningful artistic interventions that cater for local residents.

There was a debate on the activist facet of artists when they enter a territory without being requested, and the tension between artistic expression and community acceptance. Some participants shared experiences from events like the ES_CULTURA film festival, organized by A-Place, where art was used to engage the community but faced challenges due to differing perceptions and understandings. Art was acknowledged as a form of activism, although sometimes might be perceived as elitist by citizens.

The conversation also touched on the importance of quality artistic experiences accessible to all, especially in underserved neighbourhoods. The allocation of budgets for cultural projects and the impact of increasing artist presence on deprived areas were discussed. The debate highlighted that regardless of the form of art, its most significant achievement lies in sparking dialogue and debate within the community, even if controversial, emphasizing the importance of community engagement in the revalorization of public space through artistic interventions.

Figure 2.4. Debate "Art, activism, and public space"

-“The sense of place and audiovisual language”

Participants: Domènec; Elvira Pujol and Joan Vila i Puig (Sitesize); and Victoria Sacco (LOOP Barcelona). Moderated by Ruben Verdú.

In this discussion participants explored the connections between location, visual storytelling, and the impact of digital imagery (Figure 2.5). The conversation revolved around the essence of place and how it influences human experiences.

Participants acknowledged the primal nature of place is the gathering around a fire to share stories, highlighting the inherent importance of physical spaces in human interaction. They emphasized the significance of using audiovisual techniques (video and film) to capture life stories, as a means to immortalize and revisit these narratives. There was a discussion on the physical and imaginative vacuums present in many spaces, and about the role video can play to reveal and visualize those voids.

The discussion underscored the pivotal role of places in artistic expression. Artists expressed the difficulty of confining their work to predetermined scripts, emphasizing the need to let the environment guide their creative process. The conversation also delved into the abstract nature of technical imagery, and about their influence on our perception of places and the stories we create around them.

Overall, the discussion highlighted the importance of anchoring artistic endeavours in specific physical and social spaces while acknowledging the abstract complexities of the digital image, prompting artists to reconsider their methods of creating and representing places with audiovisual media.

Figure 2.5. Debate about "The sense of place and audiovisual language"

2.2.2 Interactions between music, dance and space

Roaming performances throughout the day, by Albert Vallverdú (music compositions, guitar) and Carla Camacho (dance) (Figure 2.6).

Three interactive performances involving music, dance, and space, conducted at different times during the event, brought together different artistic expressions and transformed the space. The following topics were explored:

- **Interiors and exteriors of music, dance, and space:** The first action began outdoors and transitioned indoors, guiding the participants with melodic music and moving dance. Inside, the performance continued with electric guitar music and dance, exploring the recognition of space by tracing movements in various directions.
- **Reverberations:** A long period of reverberation occurs between sound and silence. The large dimensions and elongated proportion of the interior space generate this phenomenon. The second action amplified this idea, translating it from music to dance. The musician records live musical fragments, allowing them to blend with the dancer's movements. The dancer momentarily becomes a partner in exploration, delving into the boundaries of the space.
- **Dualities:** Movement and stillness. Sound and silence. Melody and harmony. Public and non-public. Length and width. These ideas emerge in all three actions, materializing in space through improvisation.
- **Dispersion and intimacy of the performance space:** The first two actions did not delimit the space, aiming for more dispersion of the action. In the third action, a circular space was created by arranging seats in an arc. This new configuration fostered a sense of intimacy, as the audience physically delineated a sub-space within the vast hall. This arrangement allowed for profound two-way listening, enhancing the creative intensity of the moment.

Figure 2.6. Music and dance performance by Albert Vallverdú and Carla Camacho

2.2.3 Participatory collage

The purpose of this activity, facilitated by Mario Hernández from the School of Architecture La Salle, was to collaboratively create a collage representing the participants' experience of the city of L'Hospitalet (Figures 2.7-2.9).

During the activities conducted in collaboration with A-Place, students from the Systems of Representation course at the School of Architecture La Salle conducted a photographic survey of the city of L'Hospitalet (see Deliverables 4.1-4.2). A curated selection of these photographs was exhibited. Alongside the exhibition, participants collaboratively created a collage during the event, utilizing printouts of these photographs. A large city map was provided, allowing attendees to pinpoint the specific areas to which the images belonged. Subsequently, a discussion took place in front of the map, extending to the table where the photographs were displayed. The chosen images were then assembled onto the collage.

Figure 2.7-2.9. Different stages of the process of building the city collage

2.2.4 Proposals to activate Can Trinxet

Students of the “Research Seminar of Contemporary Habitat” at the School of Architecture La Salle presented their proposals to activate the community space of Can Trinxet. The session was moderated by Angel Martin Cojo, faculty member responsible of the course. Members of the association “Som Santa Eulàlia” were invited to the presentation of the proposals. A blank sheet was laid out in the exhibition space for students and other participants to summarize their ideas about the transformation of the place (Figures 2.10-2.11).

Figures 2.10-2.11. Sharing the proposals to activate Can Trinxet

2.2.5 Sensorial experience workshop

An activity organized by LEMUR (Laboratorio de Emergencias Urbanas) enabled the participants to experience the space. Within the framework of participatory design as a tool for social cohesion, strengthening community ties, and supporting an ecofeminist transformation, Lemur, Urban Emergency Laboratory's working methodology is design through the body. It involves a

series of playful dynamics that, using sensory experiences, perception, and exploration of nature as a connector, allow for reflection on well-being by experiencing the relationship between the body, movement, and space.

Participants were encouraged to connect with their own bodies and bodily memories through tactile and olfactory stimuli (Figures 2.12-2.14). The aim is to express their vision of well-being by tapping into non-verbal memories and imaginations.

Figures 2.12-2.13. Raising awareness of the tactile and olfactory senses

Figure 2.14. Engaging with the body through senses other than sight

2.3 Concert

The day concluded with an open-air concert performed by The Django Orchestra Academy from the Escola Municipal de Música Centre de les Arts de L'Hospitalet (Figures 2.15-2.16).

Figures 2.15-2.16. Concert by the Django Orchestra Academy

2.4 Exhibition

The exhibition was organized in the old factory hall from June 3 to 7, 2023 (Figures 2.17-2.18). It showcased the work carried out by the School of Architecture La Salle together with the community stakeholders during the last four years in L'Hospitalet, as well as the work done by A-Place in Bologna, Brussels, Lisbon, Ljubljana, and Nicosia. A part of the exhibition is dedicated to videos produced by A-Place and LOOP Barcelona.

Figures 2.17-2.18. Exhibition hall in the old nave of the Can Trinxet factory

The exhibition was structured in the following sections:

-A-Place: connecting places. A collective exhibition of the work done by A-Place partners, displayed on 15 panels 2m. x 1m (Figures 2.19-2.20). The panels were used by partners to explain their work to visitors (Figure 2.21). A special section was dedicated to "A Confined Place" (Figures 2.22-2.23).

Figure 2.19-2.20. Views of the exhibition displaying the work of the A-Place network.

Figure 2.21. Maria Irene Aparício, A-Place partner from NOVA, explains visitors the work done in Lisbon

Figures 2.22-2.23. Views of the section of the exhibition dedicated to "A Confined Place"

- **A-Place: L'Hospitalet.** Activities carried out by A-Place in the city of L'Hospitalet within the programme "A Weaved Place" (Figure 2.24), shown in a variety of formats (photographs, videos, panels).

Figure 2.24. Section of the exhibition dedicated to "A Weaved Place"

- **The experience of places through audiovisual language.** Projections of the [video works](#) commissioned by LOOP Barcelona for the A-Place project (Figures 2.25-2.26).

Figures 2.25-2.26. Section of the exhibition dedicated to the videos commissioned by LOOP Barcelona

- **The experience of living at home.** A re-edition of the exhibition by La Gloria Factoría de Arte which took place at La Florida neighbourhood in 2022. An [open contest](#) was organized in that

time to invite residents to represent and describe their domestic places (Figure 2.27).

Figure 2.27. Section of the exhibition "The experience of living at home"

The sound installation "Listening tables" was commissioned to Alejandro Artigas and Jimmy Solórzano for this event, which brought the sounds of L'Hospitalet and Lisbon to the exhibition hall (Figures 2.28-2.30).

Figure 2.28-2.30. Installation "Listening tables"

3. Closing Event Lisbon: Sensing places together

Maria Irene Aparício
NOVA FCSH, Lisbon

3.1 Introduction

The closing programme in Lisbon, organized by NOVA team with the support of the project coordinator, Leandro Madrazo was focused on the theme "[Sensing Places Together](#)". The event took place on the 14th and 15th of September 2023, at [Largo do Cabeço da Bola](#), in a former garrison.

After the abandonment of the installation by the national gendarmerie force in 2015 and following a change in the municipal master plan, the space was temporarily transferred, in 2022, to the [Largo Residências cooperative](#). This organization transformed the old barracks into artistic residencies for incubation and organized socio-cultural activities for social inclusion and local development. "[Sensing Places Together](#)" is the latest event hosted by this cooperative in this complex, which will become the headquarters of the Lisbon Architecture Triennial.

"Sensing Places Together" created a place by transforming the spaces of the old military installation into a shared experience. These spaces become an artistic, cultural and social meeting point, encompassing lectures and debates, artistic performances, musical concerts, exhibitions, projections and conversations on contemporary cultural and sociopolitical issues, as it is the case of homeless women.

The goal of the programme was to share experiences both among project partners and within a broader scope, with guest participants. Artists, academics, and researchers involved in processes of creation and transformation of multi-varied public spaces participated in the event. Together, we discussed themes related to the representation, experience, and transformation of urban spaces, and their influence on people's lives, and their capacity to recover memories and create new experiences.

The programme was advertised on the project website (Figure 3.1), and with the assistance of the Portuguese section of [Creative Europe](#). Guests included artists from various fields, faculty from diverse disciplines, composers, and musicians. Two keynote presentations were given by Croatian artist Branka Cvjetičanin and Elvira Pujol, from the Sitesize art collective in Barcelona. In addition to the host partner NOVA, representatives of Prostoroz, LOOP Barcelona, University of Ljubljana and La Salle-URL participated in this two-day event.

Figure 3.1 Cover of the programme

Maria Irene Aparício, from host partner NOVA, welcomed the participants at the start of the Thursday session. Leandro Madrazo, A-Place project coordinator (Figure 3.2), provided an overview of the project and the work done during the four years by the consortium.

A video documentary of the event is available [here](#).

Figure 3.2. Introduction to A-Place by Leandro Madrazo

3.2 Programme development

The first day of the conference was dedicated to the themes "Sensing Places: Artistic Interventions", "Seeing Places", and "Hearing Places". A keynote with the title "Pedestrian Viewpoint - Body Space Architecture Economy Poetry" was given by Croatian artist Branka Cvjetičanin (Figure 3.3), who talked about her art-based performative practice.

Figure 3.3. Keynote by Croatian artist Branka Cvjetičanin

The following topics were presented throughout the day: "Creating meaningful contexts through video art", by Mila Pesce, LOOP Barcelona; screening of "[La Carpa](#)", by David Bestué and Roser Corella, video commissioned by LOOP for the A-Place project (Figures 3.4, 3.5); "Inventiveness, what place(s) between art and education?", by Mara Maravilha, Polytechnic Institute of Viseu (Figure 3.6); "Identity corpus as raw material", by Lara Seixo Rodrigues, Mistaker Maker - Artistic

Intervention Platform (Figure 3.7); and "Aural Experience and Territory", by Luis Claudio Ribeiro, Lusófona University (Figure 3.8).

Figure 3.4. Presentation by Mila Pesce

Figure 3.5. Still from video "La Carpa", from David Bestué and Roser Corella

Figures 3.6. Performance by Mara Maravilha

Figure 3.7. Presentation by Lara Seixo Rodrigues

Figure 3.8. Presentation by Luis Claudio Ribeiro

On the second day, we explored the themes of "Sensing Places: Audiovisual Languages" and "Ecologies: (Re)Creating and Sensing Places." Elvira Pujol, from [Sitesize](#) (Figures 3.9, 3.10) platform dedicated to creation and research into the contemporary metropolis, delivered a keynote. She presented some of Sitesize's projects revolving around the idea of perception and resonance of places. In the second part of her presentation, Elvira interspersed her reflections with the playback of segments from the video [TERRÀpolis](#), by Elvira Pujol and Joan Vila Puig, commissioned by LOOP for A-Place.

Figure 3.9. Keynote by Elvira Pujol

Figure 3.10. Projection of the video TERRÀpolis

Other themes presented on the second day were: "Co-creating Public Spaces in Remote Places", by Matej Nikšič, Urban Planning Institute of the Republic of Slovenia, member of the [Human Cities/Smoties](#) Creative Europe project (Figure 3.11); "Landscape Museum", by Maria Joao Centeno, School of Communication and Media Studies - IPL & ICNOVA, and Joao Abreu, School of Communication and Media Studies -IPL (Figure 3.12); and "Passeio" by Helena Pires, CECS / Minho University, and Zara Pinto-Coelho, CECS / Minho University (Figure 3.13).

Figure 3.11. Presentation by Matej Nikšič

Figure 3.12. Presentation by Maria Joao Centeno and Joao Abreu

Figure 3.13. Presentation by Helena Pires and Zara Pinto-Coelho

The presentations were interspersed with moments of debate (Figures 3.14). At the end of a session, participants made a circle to continue the discussion (Figure 3.15).

Figure 3.14. Dialogue with presenters

Figure 3.15. Participants gathered in a circle to continue the discussion after the presentations

3.3 Concert

Three years after creating the soundscape of Bairro de Mouraria in "[A Sound Place](#)", the composers Jaime Reis, João Quinteiro and young composers from the Escola Superior de Música de Lisboa, as well as performers Duo Contracello (Figure 3.16) and Henrique Portovedo (Figure 3.17), re-edited the concert held in 2020 for only ten spectators at the Mouraria Innovation Center, and broadcasted across the world via streaming. This remake (2023) has new musical arrangements - one of the characteristics of contemporary erudite music - and includes a new musical piece - "Nøed.navire." - created by Jaime Reis. The original concert (2020) can be viewed [here](#); the new concert (2023) can be listened here.

Figure 3.16. Duo Contracello & Jaime Reis (composer): "A (travelling) Sound" concert

Figure 3.17. Henrique Portovedo, "Hermes, Nine O'clock"(João Quinteiro Composer) | Vídeo: Sinem Taş

The event finalized with a live concert by composer João Ferreira (electronic Organ) (Figures 3.18, 2.19), with the screening of a video essay created by the collective [Entropia](#) (João Ferreira and Marta Fiolíć, 2023) for the A-Place project. This concert-installation includes original music by João Ferreira inspired by the sounds of Bairro da Mouraria, with the aim of recreating the feelings of women of the ["Somos Mulheres" Association](#). These women lived on the streets of Lisbon, some of them for decades, and are now trying to rescue other women, in the same situation, under the leadership of Elda Coimbra (Figure 3.20). A video created by Marta Fiolíć for the A-Place project portrays the lives of these women, in parallel with her Interactive Documentary which had its premiêre almost three months after this concert-installation.

Figure 3.18. "Passages": Composer João Ferreira (electronic organ) and video essay screening by Marta Fiolic

Figure 3.19. Audience in the final audiovisual performance

Figure 3.20. Representatives of the collective “Somos Mulheres” in the event, accompanied by Marta Fiolic

The audiovisual performance *Entropia* is based on the testimonies of the women of “Somos Mulheres” that describe their livelihoods, their struggles, their setbacks, and their triumphs before, during, and after experiencing homelessness. The narratives have no beginning or ending; they reflect different passages with different odds and possibilities, while the sounds and images help the immersion in the experiences, faces, and places. The installation is envisioned as a slideshow of photographs and videos in synergy with a live musical performance using keyboards and electronics. The musical piece was created from the interviews and street sounds captured passing through the Mouraria neighbourhood, between Praça da Figueira and Intendente, relevant for the individual stories.

3.4 Exhibition

In parallel with the conference, and in an adjacent space, the thirteen panels produced by coordinating team were exhibited both printed and pasted on the dilapidated wall. In addition, a video composed with the contents of the panels was projected on the walls, highlighting specific moments from the project activities (Figure 3.21). This video, as well as all the videos created by project partners, were permanently on display during the two days of the conference. During the event, some of the discussions took place at the exhibition space (Figure 3.22).

Figure 3.21. Exhibition space

Figure 3.22. Dialogue with composers in the exhibition space

4. Annex - Exhibition panels

These panels are available on the project [website](#) in .pdf format, in English, Spanish and Catalan.

A-Place

Linking places through networked artistic practices

A-Place aims to encourage creation, experimentation and debate on the sense of place and belonging in our interconnected and multicultural societies. This project brings together artists, creators, architects, teachers, students from various educational levels and cultural

A-Place is a project co-financed by the Creative Europe programme from 2019 to 2023. Its aim is to enhance the bonds between people and the places they inhabit in six European cities: Barcelona, Bologna, Brussels, Lisbon, Ljubljana, and Nicosia.

agents who collaborate with communities to create a network of places —tangible and intangible— that promotes exchange between people and cultures, overcoming geographical and disciplinary boundaries.

<https://a-place.eu/>

A-Place partnership includes nine organizations:

- Schools of architecture and urban planning**
 - School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona (Spain)
 - Faculty of Architecture, University of Ljubljana (Slovenia)
 - KU Leuven, Department of Architecture (Belgium)

- Faculty of social and human sciences**
 - Universidade Nova de Lisboa and Nova FCSH (Portugal)

- Multidisciplinary groups focusing on arts and urban interventions**
 - Alive Architecture (Belgium)
 - Prostoroz (Slovenia)
 - Urban Gorillas (Cyprus)

- Cultural agencies specialised in film and video art**
 - Screen Projects (Spain)
 - City Space Architecture (Italy)

Co-funded by the Creative Europe Programme of the European Union

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Celebrating vibrant places

There is a need for public spaces that foster social interaction, community engagement and the physical and mental health of the city's inhabitants. These places not only generate economic benefits, but also contribute to reducing crime and improving safety, while strengthening the sense of belonging and identity of the community.

community engagement, healthy environments, **public space**: a crucial component of placemaking, quality of life, well-being

A Delicious Place

Partners: Urban Gorillas
Location: Kaimakli neighbourhood, Nicosia
Date: July - September 2020

The Pame Kaimakli festival hosted a series of events centred on the theme of food as a socio-cultural and placemaking activity. The festival's centrepiece was the creation of a Vertical Garden, a community garden located in the central square of the neighbourhood. This garden served as the venue for various activities such as performances, communal dinners, a pop-up cinema, and a meeting point for both residents and visitors.

A-Pla(y)ce

Partners: Faculty of Architecture, University of Ljubljana and ProstorOž
Location: Bežigrjski Dvor district, Ljubljana
Date: March - May 2021

The neighbourhood lacks a consolidated social history and identity. Alleys are spaces that have great potential for creating places to socialise and play. Architecture students, mentors, experts, and children worked together to transform alleys into a playscape. Activities included consultation meetings with community representatives, new facility design and the realization of a "placemaking" intervention.

A Weaved Place

Partners: School of Architecture La Salle
Location: Bellvitge neighbourhood, L'Hospitalet de Llobregat (Barcelona)
Date: November 2022

The ES_CULTURA festival turned the Plaça de la Cultura in Bellvitge into a vibrant hub for artistic expression, with the participation of students from local schools, architecture students, artists, local residents, and civic organization members. Throughout the two-day event, the square and its surroundings were transformed through sculptures, murals, film projections, sound installations, as well as music and dance performances.

A Wish-full Place

Partners: Urban Gorillas
Location: City Plaza, Nicosia
Date: October-December 2021

City Plaza is an old shopping centre located in Nicosia that once housed a bustling major department store and attracted a number of visitors, but in recent years it has experienced a decline. To revitalize the space and encourage people to rediscover it, ephemeral interventions are taking place. In this intervention, visitors were invited to participate in origami workshops and write their wishes on folded papers. These messages were then thrown onto hanging canvases, filling in this way the space with people's wishes.

Building engaged communities

Living in community involves commitment, caring, and togetherness. When people have common interests, strong bonds are created that can lead to a shared sense of identity. If they feel like they are part of a larger group with shared values, they are more likely to work together towards common goals, care for each other and invest their time and energy in building resilient and sustainable communities.

commitment, care, collective identity, common interests, **community building**: engaging people to create spaces responsive to their needs and desires, place attachment

A Visionary Place

Partners: City Space Architecture
Location: Porto-Saragozza neighbourhood, Bologna
Date: September-November 2020

The goal of the parklet is to enliven public spaces through creative and educational projects. This new public space serves as a community hub, offering a venue for social interaction, artistic performances, and communal gatherings. Additionally, the parklet has been instrumental in fostering a sense of community through the creation of a Facebook page, where valuable insights and lessons about the experience of creating this new public space can be shared with other communities beyond the neighbourhood.

A Happy Place

Partners: Alive Architecture, in collaboration with BRAVVO
Location: Marolles neighbourhood, Brussels
Date: April - June 2021

With the aim of making Pieremans' playground a livable and happy place, a series of events were held to get to know the interests and wishes of the residents. During these events, ideas and problems were identified and discussed, and participants wrote them down on sticky paper and stuck them on a model of the site. Four workshops were organised to test the proposed ideas. The transformed spaces were inaugurated at a community event, where a collective meal was prepared to celebrate the outcome of the project.

A Future Place

Partners: Universidade Nova de Lisboa
Location: Padre Cruz neighbourhood, Lisbon
Date: September-November 2021

Universidade Nova collaborated with the Amigos da Luz association to organize a literary contest "My neighbourhood... my place" that allowed young people and adults to share their experiences of living in Padre Cruz neighbourhood through prose and poetry. The winners read their texts in a prize ceremony that was held in a parking area in front of the association, which was transformed into a stage for a few hours. Between readings of the texts, a young musician delighted the audience with his fado songs on guitar. The event brought together the local community and provided an excellent platform for artistic expression.

*"I always said and proudly
 I'm from the neighbourhood,
 Yes sir!
 I was raised with respect
 In the neighbourhood,
 we felt love*

*We had the time for everything
 Studying, working, living
 together.
 We had great fun*

*In moments of leisure
 we decorated the streets
 and jumped over the fire
 we burned artichokes
 we played well*

*There were three associations
 it's sad because they ended
 I congratulate you
 for the project you started*

*The history of our neighbourhood
 that was told in a book
 I advise you to read it
 a lot has been changed"*

Author: by a European female resident

Reinforcing a sense of place and belonging

A sense of place is a unique combination of visual, cultural and environmental factors that give a location its distinct character. This encompasses the memories, emotions, and perceptions that people associate with a place, making it special and meaningful to them. When communities cultivate and celebrate the unique qualities and characteristics of a place, they can foster a sense of identity, promote well-being, and drive economic growth.

collective memory, place identity, **sense of belonging**: creating places that foster a sense of pride and ownership among community members, sense of place

A Hidden Place

© Urban and Planning Dept. Ljubljana

Photography by Šteja Vlahovič and Anja Čižar Milčević

© City of Ljubljana

© Municipality of Ljubljana

Partners: Faculty of Architecture, University of Ljubljana and Prostoroz
Location: "Krater" area, Bežigranski Dvor, Ljubljana
Date: March – June 2020

A series of events was planned to re-discover a long-forgotten place, involving residents, teachers from nearby schools, parents, and relatives of children and young people, as well as passers-by. However, due to COVID-19 restrictions, residents could only participate through distant communication. Based on their suggestions, architecture students proposed creative and thought-provoking interventions to make the site attractive to a wide audience.

A Place of Our Own

© Architecture Department KU Leuven

"Sense of place is what makes one city different from another, but sense of place is also what makes our physical surroundings worth caring about."
 Edward T. McMahon

© KU Leuven

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Partners: KU Leuven Department of Architecture
Location: Bodegem Foyer shelter, Brussels
Date: April – May 2021

Bodegem Foyer is just one of many homeless shelters located in the centre of Brussels. Architecture students, shelter residents, neighbours, and activists have collaborated to transform the shelter, upcycling the materials found in the building into new furniture pieces. Students and residents received training in furniture building with ecological materials in a workshop held in the shelter. The outcome was a more hospitable living environment that fostered an increased sense of ownership and belonging among the residents.

A Happy Place

© Alive Architecture

© Alive Architecture

© Alive Architecture

© Alive Architecture

Partners: Alive Architecture, in collaboration with BRAVVO
Location: Marolles neighbourhood, Brussels
Date: April – June 2022

To make Pieremans playground more attractive to residents, permanent urban interventions were carried out, including the construction of an urban garden and a fence to protect it. In the alleys of the Cité Hellémans, residents painted and installed planters on the balconies of their homes. These renovated spaces were celebrated with an inauguration event that included food, music and video projections showing the transformation process.

A Place of Our Own

© KU Leuven

Partners: KU Leuven Department of Architecture
Location: Bodegem Foyer shelter, Brussels
Date: November 2021

KUL students organised a participatory action to paint a mural on the wall in the lobby of the Bodegem shelter, which included the personal stories of the residents. The creation of the mural provided an opportunity to apply our community engagement methodologies, encouraging residents' involvement in creating a visual identity for their shelter and making it "their place".

Evoking sensory awareness and a feeling for our places

The senses play a crucial role in our perception and understanding of places. They allow us to experience and learn about the unique qualities and characteristics of a place, such as its aesthetic, cultural, social and environmental features. Sights and sounds can evoke feelings of excitement and energy, smells can bring back childhood memories, and textures can evoke a sense of rootedness and continuity, connecting us with the past. In this way, our sensory experiences help us to connect with the places we inhabit.

foodscapes, sensorial spaces, soundscapes, **space perception**: seeing, hearing, touching, tasting, and smelling the environment around us

A Calm Place

After the walk, leaving traces of the red ribbons. Source: Alvo Architecture

Courtyard of Maison des Arts during the Blind Art Contest. Source: Alvo Architecture

Walking map - the experience of the sensory walk. Source: Alvo Architecture

A community dinner with food and drinks. Source: Alvo Architecture

Partners: Alvo Architecture and KU Leuven Department of Architecture
Location: Schaerbeek district, Brussels
Date: October 2020

In this sensory walk, participants were able to improve their spatial awareness by focusing on sounds, smells and textures. They were taken to various locations in the neighbourhood to perceive the calmness. Participants were blindfolded to increase the sensitivity of non-visual senses. The walk ended in the garden of the Maison des Arts, where participants reflected on their experiences and wrote them on a red ribbon to create a collective art installation.

A Weaved Place

sense of belonging

Partners: School of Architecture La Salle
Location: La Florida neighbourhood, L'Hospitalet de Llobregat (Barcelona)
Date: June 2021

During a walk through the neighbourhood, members of Espai Jove Sidecar, a community initiative aimed at preventing the social exclusion of young people, and the neighbourhood association Districte IV met to explore the area. Throughout the tour, older residents shared their memories and explained how the neighbourhood had been transformed over time. These stories were unfamiliar to many of the young people, most of whom came from other countries. At the end of the walk, participants placed printed photographs taken along the way on a map and shared their experiences.

A Reconnecting Place

Co-creating a choreography. Source: Alvo Architecture

Recording the sounds of the neighbourhood

Partners: Universidade Nova de Lisboa
Location: Rego neighbourhood, Lisbon
Date: January-September 2022

A programme of co-creative activities around sound and movement was designed with and for children and young people from the Passa Sabi association. The activities included the creation of a music piece inspired by the neighbourhood soundscape, a sound walking experience to capture the sounds, the co-creation of a choreography, and a flash mob performance to showcase the music and dance created collaboratively.

A Delicious Place

"Sensory experiences are intimately intertwined with perceptual memories that mediate the present moment of experience in various ways: by multiplying, judging and dulling the sensory encounter"

Monica Degen

Partners: Urban Gorillas
Location: Kaimakli neighbourhood, Nicosia
Date: September 2020

During the Pame Kaimakli Festival, a series of video stories revolving around the theme of food were presented. The videos documented various artist-led initiatives that used theatre, storytelling and performance to engage migrants and residents in culinary activities. The videos were screened in a pop-up cinema alongside videos created by A-Place organisations on themes of food, community and public space.

■ Growing sustainability awareness

Raising awareness about the presence of nature in our daily lives, naturalising the city and promoting the circular economy are fundamental aspects to foster sustainability and build a more environmentally responsible society. Communities can contribute to a sustainable future by incorporating green infrastructure, educating people, encouraging recycling, promoting renewable energy sources, and using non-polluting transportation.

carbon footprint, nature, sustainable practices, vegetation, **urban ecology: a place includes natural systems, resources, and habitats that exist within and around it,** waste

A Re-place

Partners: Faculty of Architecture, University of Ljubljana and ProstoRož
Location: "Kratar" area, Bežigrasjski Dvor, Ljubljana
Date: March – April 2022

Residents, visitors, activists and community representatives were invited to discuss their ideas on the revitalisation of the area known as "Kratar". Architecture students designed and installed public infrastructure using materials found in the area. Their proposals were based on circular design and reuse of materials, going beyond the conventional take-make-waste extractive model.

A Hidden Place

Partners: Faculty of Architecture, University of Ljubljana and ProstoRož
Location: "Kratar" area, Bežigrasjski Dvor, Ljubljana
Date: August 2020

To transform an empty space into a liveable place for people, ProstoRož collaborated with the local community to explore the potential uses of plants found in the area. A meal (burek) was organized using local plants, which allowed people to discover the flora, its origin, and its impact on the environment.

A Seedling Place

Partners: Urban Gorillas
Location: Kaimakli neighbourhood, Nicosia
Date: April-July 2022

During the Pame Kaimakli festival, the Forestry Department and the Municipality of Nicosia collaborated in a series of urban reforestation actions. A Vertical Garden was created along the disused railway tracks with 100 aromatic plants planted by neighbours. This temporary installation became permanent, and residents took turns caring for the plants, creating an attractive and sustainable place. They also planted 70 small trees in public spaces, schools and cultural institutions.

A Seedling Place

Partners: Urban Gorillas, Alive Architecture, City Space Architecture and ProstoRož
Location: Cyprus pavilion, Venice Biennale
Date: October 2021

The installation at the Cyprus Pavilion of the Venice Biennale 2021 was a continuation of the Vertical Gardens installed in Kaimakli, Nicosia. Visitors to the Biennale were invited to plant and tend a community garden with seeds brought from A-Place partner cities. There was also an activity that involved Biennale visitors in a planting initiative shared through A-Place's social media.

Building creative societies

Public spaces provide an open platform for artistic expression, where artists and communities can bring their visions to life, explore new ideas and connect with others through shared experiences. By promoting the use of public spaces as territories for artistic creation, cities can encourage cultural diversity, foster creativity, promote social cohesion and contribute to energising urban life.

cultural diversity, **collective creativity**: art and creativity help to create aesthetically compelling, culturally relevant, and socially engaging places, shared spaces, urban art

A Weaved Place

Partners: School of Architecture La Salle
Location: Bellvitge neighbourhood, L'Hospitalet de Llobregat (Barcelona)
Date: April-November 2021

Personal memories and experiences related to places often go unnoticed in the public sphere. In order to highlight the importance of certain places in the Bellvitge neighbourhood, secondary school students were encouraged to identify places that had a special value for them. The architecture students then proposed interventions to share the significance of these places. Finally, they all collaborated in setting up the installations in the public space.

collective creativity

collective creativity

A Sound Place

Partners: Universidade Nova de Lisboa
Location: Mouraria neighbourhood, Lisbon
Date: March - April 2020

Inspired by the real and imaginary sounds of Mouraria and the experiences of Martim Moniz Square, young composers created musical pieces in the style of contemporary classical music. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the concert could not be held in the square as originally planned. Instead, the pieces were performed and streamed live from the Mouraria Innovation Centre. As originally planned, the concert played in the public space would inspire people to re-imagine the surroundings through the music pieces crafted from the very places they were in.

A Calm Place

"Imagine society without the influence of the arts and you'll have to strip out what is most pleasurable in life, and much that is educationally vital."
 Peter Bazalgette

Partners: Alive Architecture and KU Leuven Department of Architecture
Location: Schaerbeek district, Brussels
Date: October 2020

Master's students from KU Leuven's "Alt-Shift" course led a community workshop aimed at introducing the public to recycling materials through a hands-on, do-it-yourself approach. The activity focused on experimenting with design techniques to create foldable furniture using leftover cardboard boxes. Prior to the workshop, the same techniques were explored by students during the spring semester's design course. This inclusive activity was open to people of all ages who were interested in participating.

A Confined Place

Partners: La Salle-URL, Universidade Nova de Lisboa, University of Ljubljana, Urban Gorillas and City Space Architecture
Location: Online
Date: March - December 2020

In response to the 2020 lockdown, students from higher education institutions in A-Place collaborated to share their experiences with lived spaces by means of photographs and texts. Creators from around the world participated in an open call for artistic interventions in public spaces in time of confinement. Filmmakers from different countries submitted their short films about public space during the lockdown to the "A Confined Urban Vision" call.

collective creativity

Celebrating diversity and inclusiveness

Diversity and inclusion are key components of a healthy and thriving urban community. By embracing diversity, we can enrich our communities with a broader range of perspectives, experiences and ideas, contributing to a more inclusive society. Inclusion also helps to create a more equitable environment, where everyone has the opportunity to participate and contribute, regardless of their background or identity.

coexistence, design justice, diversity, multiculturality, **social inclusion: promoting diversity, equity, and accessibility for creating inclusive environments**

A Just Place

Video in podcast at the Grand Hospice

Video in podcast at the Grand Hospice

Installation at the Grand Hospice

Partners: Department of Architecture, KU Leuven
Location: Grand Hospice, Brussels
Date: February-May 2022

The Grand Hospice provided an exhibition space and co-working room for a live radio podcast studio showcasing the work of master students from the Architecture Design Justice Studio. The focus was on spatial justice in Brussels, in particular on homelessness and transigrant communities. The podcasts featured interviews with architects, students, NGOs, and activists. The exhibition included a comparative research project on temporary occupations, questioning the values, narratives, practices, sites, and pedagogies of supporting organizations.

A Weaved Place

Installation at the Hospitalet de Llobregat

Partners: School of Architecture I a Salle
Location: La Florida neighbourhood, L'Hospitalet de Llobregat (Barcelona)
Date: June 2022

The Florida neighbourhood is a densely populated area of L'Hospitalet, inhabited mainly by low-income immigrants and characterized by low-quality housing with tiny flats. Residents were invited to share their home-life experiences through photographs and texts. Artists from La Gloria Factoria de Arte curated the works and assembled them on the outer wall of the neighbourhood's civic centre. This installation provided an opportunity for personal experiences of domestic spaces to be shared in a public space.

A Hidden Place

Search for vegetables in the hidden place

Prep'g, burek

social inclusion

Arrive at the hidden place for the preparation, gathering, listening

Partners: Prostoroz
Location: Božigrjski Dvor, Ljubljana
Date: August 2020

This community dinner brought attention to a long-forgotten place hidden behind a fence. Burek, an imported but well-accepted dish brought by migrants from Bosnia, was cooked using plants found on the site. The meal helped to highlight the value of combining cultures and places. The event was videotaped and presented at the Pame Kaimakli festival in Nicosia, thus promoting cultural diversity across geographical borders and connections between places.

A Reconnecting Place

Market in the Rego neighbourhood

Installation in Rego

Market in Rego neighbourhood

Partners: Universidade Nova de Lisboa
Location: Rego neighbourhood, Lisbon
Date: January-September 2022

Rego is a diverse neighbourhood that is home to a mix of immigrants and residents of all ages. Urban art and cultural development projects can help bring these diverse social groups together and foster a shared sense of belonging. Through a series of artistic performances with music and dance, people were encouraged to develop collective identity, strengthening their ties and sense of belonging to the neighbourhood.

Creating learning places

Educational activities in communities can give rise to new places of learning that transcend the boundaries between academia and society, between formal and informal learning, and between different subjects, academic levels and disciplines. In addition, these places encourage the transfer of knowledge and skills between community members and academia, fostering interdisciplinary and intergenerational learning.

action learning, project-based learning, **situated learning**: creating environments that support active and experiential learning where individuals can engage with their surroundings

A Re-place

Planning the layout and layout of involved case for Blue

Partners: Faculty of Architecture, University of Ljubljana and Prostorož
Location: "Krater" area, Bežigranski Dvor, Ljubljana
Date: March - April 2022

A dynamic learning platform brought together experts, students and community members to exchange their experiences and views with the aim of revitalising the "Krater" area. The site was transformed into a place of learning by hosting lively discussions on the need for recycling and reuse in urban design, as well as on the protection of natural resources in cities.

A-Pla(y)ce

Open consultation and discussion of the proposals with invited local community representatives

Partners: Faculty of Architecture, University of Ljubljana and Prostorož
Location: Bežigranski Dvor, Ljubljana
Date: March-May 2021

Play can contribute to a sense of joy, creativity, and community engagement. Residents became involved in the co-creation of a new place by responding to questionnaires prepared by students to understand their needs and visions. The proposed interventions were then presented to local community representatives and exhibited in the neighbourhood. In a closing event, residents, students, and mentors discussed possibilities and options for the implementation of the designs.

A Weaved Place

Active use of a public space by the students for processing information in school

Partners: School of Architecture La Salle
Location: Bellvitge neighbourhood, L'Hospitalet de Llobregat (Barcelona)
Date: April - November 2021

High school students from Institut Bellvitge documented their personal experiences in nearby public spaces through photographs and texts, which they shared with architecture students from La Salle. They proposed interventions in the public space to represent these experiences, and a joint meeting was organised in the Plaça de la Cultura to discuss the proposals. Through these activities, the public space became a place of learning.

A Happy Place

The process of the running traces for local theme source: Alive Architecture

Partners: Alive Architecture, in collaboration with BRAVVO
Location: Marolles neighbourhood, Brussels
Date: April - June 2022

Residents were invited to participate in workshops to co-design and co-produce temporary urban interventions to make Pieremans' courtyard more liveable. During the workshops, residents made proposals for the design and placement of new pieces of street furniture, and were trained to collaborate in their construction. In addition, musical performances were organised to attract neighbours, who were also invited to share meals on site.

situated learning

Festivals

The A-Place project involves three festivals: LOOP Barcelona, Urban Visions in Bologna and Pame Kaimakli in Nicosia. In these festivals a special section is dedicated to A-Place where creative and artistic content such as videos, films and installations are produced and shared. In addition, intercultural debates and public events related to art, community and public space are organised.

LOOP Barcelona

LOOP Barcelona is an annual contemporary art festival dedicated to video art and moving image practices. Each year, the festival launches an open call as part of the A-Place project, in which proposals to produce a video are selected and evaluated by a jury of experts. In addition, LOOP invites an artist-in-residence to investigate place construction practices using audiovisual media. The video works produced by the resident artist and those selected through the open call are premiered and exhibited in the A-Place section of the festival. In addition, debates and meetings with professionals are organised to exchange knowledge and discuss the role of artists and artistic media, especially video art, in creating a sense of place.

"Terràpolis", Sitesize, LOOP artists-in-residence, 2020

Pame Kaimakli

Pame Kaimakli is an annual festival that provides an interdisciplinary platform for local communities to connect with global arts. Through creative interventions involving residents and artists, the concepts of publicness, co-creation and community engagement are explored. The festival has hosted various A-Place activities. In 2020, videos on the thematic of food and placemaking were screened in a pop-up cinema. In addition, three community dinners, cooking workshops and guided walks were organised. In the 2022 edition, selected works from the LOOP Barcelona and Urban Visions festivals were screened in a pop-up cinema. Alongside this, there were several urban reforestation activities, community dinners, and debates on the role of festivals an artists in creating a sense of place and community in A-Place.

Workshops with We Circle collective, Pame Kaimakli, 2020

Urban Visions

The aim of this film festival is to foster a dialogue between urban theory, social dynamics and film studies, and to raise awareness of the relationship between individuals and the urban spaces they inhabit. To this end, the A-Place section of the festival organises short film competitions on the themes "Migrants, Refugees and Displaced Communities" and "Resilient Communities". After a curatorial selection process of the submitted films, a jury awards the prizes during the festival where the winning and shortlisted works are screened.

Urban Visions festival 2022

Representing and creating places

The sense of place can be expressed and conveyed through different media, such as photographs, videos, music, dance, installations and texts. Each of these media has its own way of representing and communicating the essence of a place, which can provoke differ-

ent reactions, intellectual and emotional in the beholder. Moreover, artistic interventions can physically and symbolically transform public spaces, giving them new meanings.

Photographs

The photographs represent a place in isolation from the spatial continuum. They capture the physical atmosphere of a space at a particular moment in time, through the perspective of the photographer and according to the technical characteristics of the camera. In addition, photographs can convey social and cultural aspects of a place that contribute to its identity, and thus evoke emotions and memories related to it in the viewer.

"A new sublime", Ifakki Yésente, A-Place MAPPING contest, 2022

"8:00 pm", Irene de la Garza, A Confined Place, 2020

"Silence", Catarina Cabral, A Confined Place, 2020

"Matryoshka's evolution", Arkua Bogdan, A Confined Place, 2020

"Wild and Free", Azba' Anas'1, A-Place MAPPING contest, 2022

"The Unknown", Marina Papadakis, A-Place MAPPING contest, 2021

Videos

Videos have the ability to capture the life of a place and its temporal dimension, through moving images and sound. They allow for observation and analysis of the relationships between people and the places they inhabit, as expressed through their actions and words.

"La città dentro", Anna de Mainvillat/Zimmerfrei, LOOP Open Call, 2020

"I Can Only Dance to One Song", Anash Fayer, LOOP Open Call, 2021

"A journey to L'Hospitalet de Llobregat", Claudio Zuban, A Weaved Place, 2022

"Quarantine Mood", Alessandro Marinelli, A Confined Urban Vision, 2020

"La Carpa", David Bestué and Roser Cova la, LOOP artists in residence, 2021

"Terroçpolis", Slenza, LOOP artists in residence, 2020

Sounds

The character of a place is not only defined by its visual aspects but also by its audio ambience. The sounds that bounce off surfaces, the voices of the inhabitants speaking different languages, and the music playing in the streets or emanating from windows, all contribute to the cultural diversity that defines a location.

"Soundwalking", A Reconnecting Place, Lisbon, 2022

"Electromagnetic neighbourhood", A Reconnecting Place, Lisbon, 2022

"Rehearsal", A Sound Place, Lisbon, 2022

"Mentira", Marta Domingues, A Sound Place, Lisbon, 2022

"Lugar Comum", Ana Rouse, A Sound Place, Lisbon, 2022

"Ulisses'po", Mariana Ribeiro, A Sound Place, Lisbon, 2022

Texts

A place can be described through both prose and poetry. The narration of memories reveals the links that people have with a place and enables them to share personal stories. Poems, in particular, are effective at expressing the sense of attachment to a place through the use of symbolic language that evokes vivid images and emotions.

"O meu bairro", Ivan Lirinha, A Future Place, 2021

"O futuro do bairro", Tomás Estevedo, A Future Place, 2021

"Memórias do Bairro", Luis Moreira, A Future Place, 2021

"Sempre disse", Leopoldina Botelho, A Future Place, 2021

"Bairro Padre Cruz", Cátia Botelho, A Future Place, 2021

"Nasci no Bairro", Ricardo Palma, A Future Place, 2021

Objects

Objects installed in public spaces, whether as stand-alone pieces or incorporated into urban infrastructure, have the capacity to signal a place and draw attention to it. The connection that is established between the object and the viewers is fundamental to signify a place.

"Bureau", Nerea Mejias, Inês Moa, Maria Rosa Gavín and Paula Diaz, ES_CULTURA Festival, L'Hospitalet de Llobregat, 2022

Charlotta Viti, Lina Eva Pešarević, Eva Kocij, Helena Šušteršič and Veronika Šušteršič, A Re-Place, Ljubljana, 2022

Siron Deriaz, A Happy Place, Durban, Africa Architecture, 2022

Re-signifying urban infrastructure, A Weaved Place, L'Hospitalet de Llobregat, 2021

"Fill the gap", Anna Trasserra, ES_CULTURA Festival, L'Hospitalet de Llobregat, 2022

"Vertical Garden", Ajla Varvara Square, Nicosia

Performances

Performances in public spaces have the capacity to activate a place and attract people. They help to revitalise public spaces that may be underused or neglected, transforming them into spaces in which to develop creativity. They also bring people together and foster the creation of a sense of community and connection to a place.

Flash mob, A Reconnecting Place, Lisbon, October 2022

A Delicious Place, Ljubljana, August 2020

Da n'Artis seniors association, ES_CULTURA Festival, L'Hospitalet de Llobregat (Barcelona), November 2022

A Delicious Place, Nicosia, July-August 2020

Stamiriga performance, A Visionary Place, Biograd, November 2020

Pop-up cinema, Pame kaimaké festival, Nicosia, 2020

Digital places

In today's digital age, the global culture is characterised by a continuous flow of images that are transmitted through digital networks. Consequently, our perceptions of the environment are deeply influenced by these media. The contemporary sense of place is experienced in digital spaces that transcend geographical and cultural boundaries, connecting people and places from around the world.

A-Place: Mapping

The online platform, specifically designed for A-Place, facilitates activities that aim to share people's experiences of places from around the world. These activities include two contests: "Share your experience of places" and "Share your artworks in places."

Share your experience of places

In this contest, participants are invited to share their experiences of places with a photograph and a text. An international, multidisciplinary jury evaluates the submissions and awards prizes based on the following criteria:

- The uniqueness and originality of the place and of the related experience.
- The ability of the photographer to capture the characteristics of the place and to evoke the narrated experience.
- The literary value of the text in itself and in relation to the photograph.

Share your artworks in places

This contest is aimed at those who have transformed or created places through artistic interventions. The multidisciplinary jury awards prizes considering:

- The aesthetics of the intervention and its ability to integrate art, architecture, and landscape.
- The level of community involvement in the process of creating the place.
- The transformative power of the intervention, its impact on the community and on the built environment.

Would you like to share your experiences of places with us? Just send us a photograph and a brief text to accompany it!

